

Bekimon in Social Networking Site: Modernized Idiolect and Sociolect

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Abstract

The research was conducted and found out that most social media user used Filipino Language, Cross Cultural Language, Ilocano, Bicol, English, Japanese, Spanish and sward speak language including, jejemon, natural language, Language of artists such as Ansaveh, Anonuy, Anyare, B.Y, Bari-bari, Beyeen, Boom Panes, Boses palaka, Chenelyn, Chillax, Chuket, Cno sya ang lakas ng dating, Dabarkadz, Di ba pueding, eOwh phFou, GGSS, Havey Ibenta na yan, #kumakathniel, Ikawchi, Ishipiship, Istorya tupo tupo, Jaya-jaya, Julianis Morisette, Kalaban, Kitakits, Keribels, Korek, Kuya Germs, Low bat naba, Madlang People, Major Major, Matubis, Miskol, Moom manes, Murat, Nakakagoodvibes, Nga nga, No mamati ka ti magic, Oblation, Ola amiga, Pag may time, Pasok sa banga, Payreted, PDAF, Push pa more, Pwamiz, Shotimis ites, Syukit, Senti, Tapsilog, Ting ting cojuangco, Trending, Wa apple, Wapacles, Wititit, Wenno tunno lumagto jay bato, Yangku, Zsa zsa padilla. The researcher proved also that most of the words used are the sociolect in the social networking site and this are Selfie with 8 netizens user, Wakobet with 4 netizens user, Peg with an 4 netizens user, kalurkey, Epek, Anyare, Push mo yan, Groufie, Emo, Que Keri, at Ampatuan with 3 netizens user. The researcher also agreed that most of the netizens user is used different way on how to construct words such as Onomatopoeia, Addition affixes and suffixes, Invention of new words, Similarity in color, Gender Implications, Used of money as a symbol of name, Substitution of used of different vowels and replace vowels like ja, je, ji, jo, ju; cha, che, chi, cho, chu; o sha, she, shi, sho, shu at su, kyu, bu, Borrowed language locally, nationally and internationally. Additional of meaning that was connected to real life, Borrowed from the whole meaning, Jejemon, Similarity in a song, Replaced of vowels, Creating of new words, Shortened, Old words that has new meaning this mean that Filipino Language is dynamic. Based on the research findings, the researcher determine the most effective way of creating words on social networking sites. Seven (7) most commonly used methods of generating words abbreviation (49) rank number 1, followed by borrowed word from different language with (31) rank 2, word multiplication with (30) rank 3, word invention with (28) rank 4, likeness to personality (21) rank 5, add word from the original text with (20) rank 6, Jejemons spelling(35) rank 7.

Keywords: Bekimon, Social Networking Site, Idiolect and Sociolect, etc.

INTRODUCTION

Our language is rich and dynamic because it is a reflection of our culture, literature and a developing country like the Philippines. For this reason its' dynamic and adaptive being used it does not allow the time to leave and its good result is constantly changing and in return adding new and unique words and it is widely accepted by the audience or the Filipino people. The researchers proved the following objectives.

- ⦿ Identify the words used on the social networking site, the most frequently used words and the languages of the social networking site;
- ⦿ Determine the meaning of words and new ways of building words construction used on social networking sites; and
- ⦿ Determine the most effective way of building words on social networking sites.

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Independent Variable

Dependent Variable

Figure 1. The conceptual paradigm shows independently the Bekimon Social Networking Site as independent variable and dependent variable Modern Idiolect and Sociolect.

METHODS

- ⦿ Descriptive Method
- ⦿ The researcher copy ten words on Facebook, Twitter and Blogspot from 65 respondents online on the internet with a total of 65 respondents (38) in Facebook twitter (20) frequency count and (7) for blogspot.
- ⦿ **Five categories of the Respondents:** Adults, Teenagers, Gay, men, and women.
- ⦿ Frequency count
- ⦿ The research conducted August 11, 13, 14, 15, 20, 22, 26, 27, 28 September 8, 9, 12, 18, 19, 29, 30, October 1, 4, 6 and 7 in the 2014-2015 period .

The researcher used the account rachelramos@yahoo.com, junjuners@yahoo.com, on Facebook, and Sannypinto_o6, nujnujramos18, on twitter June 98.2 on the blog serves as the account for doing this study.

INTERPRETATION OF DATA AND RESULTS

The researcher used table to illustrate the outcomes of the carried out research through the table identifying the specific outcomes of the questions.

SELECTED WORDS USED ON SOCIAL NETWORKING SITES

Table 1 shows the words used by respondents on the Social Networking Site used by the respondents in social networking site from the category of the *adult*.

Words used in social networking site	Frequency	Interpretation
#Throwback	1	Pagbabalik(Return)
Anong petsa na?	1	Ang tagal gumalaw (slow motion)
Answeet	1	Ang sweet(So sweet)
Aya	1	Ilokanong sambitlang inya o ganun. (Ilokano word meaning like that or okay?)
CCTV	1	Isang surveillance system(one surveillance system)

Table 2. Frequency Count and the meaning of the words used by the respondents in social networking site from the category of the *youth*.

Words used in social networking site	Frequency	Interpretation
eOwh phFou	1	Jejemon na salita na ibig sabihin sa Ingles at Filipino ay Hello Po. (Jejemon word which means Hello in English and Filipino)
Groufie	3	Pagkuha ng larawan sa isang grupo sa pamamagitan ng digital camera. (Capturing picture as a group through digital camera)
Selfie	8	Pagkuha ng sariling larawan sa pamamagitan ng digital camera o cellphone.(Capturing yourself through digital camera or cell phone)
Push mo yan	4	Panghikayat na salita para pagbutihan pa lalo. (Inspiring word to encourage someone to make his or her work better)
(GGSS)	2	Gandang Ganda Sa Sarili. (Look so very beautiful at her ownself)

Table 3. Frequency Count and the meaning of the words used by the respondents in social networking site from the category of the *gays*.

Words used in social networking site	Frequency	Interpretation and Translation
Ampatuan	3	Salitang bakla na ibig sabihin ay oo. (Gay word means yes)
Douglas MacArthur	1	Salitang bakla na ibig sabihin ay aso. (Gay word means dog)
Kuya Germs	1	Salitang bakla na ibig sabihin ay madumi. (gay word means dirty)
Shotimis ites	1	Maitim ito. (This is dark)
Wakobet	4	Ayaw ko nito o hindi ko gusto (I don't want this or I don't like this)

Table 4. Frequency Count and the meaning of the words used by the respondents in social networking site from the category of the *boys*.

Mga salitang ginagamit sa social networking site	Frequency	Interpretation and Translation
Tapsilog	1	Isang uri ng pagkain. (A kind of food)
Yakapsul	1	Pagyakap (Hug)
Yangku	1	Kuyang (Brother)
Low bat naba	1	Sinasabi sa mga taong hindi makontak ang mga mahal nila sa cellphone. (Words they say when their love one doesn't answer their phone call)
Lutong Makaw	1	Nandaya (Cheated)

Table 5. Frequency Count and the meaning of the words used by the respondents in social networking site from the category of the *girls*.

Words used in social networking site	Frequency	Interpretation and Translation
Chismax	1	Usapang too the max (Conversation to the max)
Sino siya ang lakas ng dating	1	Hanep kung tignan o astig siya (He is so cool)
Di ba pueding	1	Pagkomento(Giving comment)
Hashtag	4	Ito’y may simbololo na #. (It has rhe symbol #)
Kathniel	1	Tawag sa mga fans ni Kathryn Bernardo at Daniel Padilla (What they call to the die hard fans of Kathryn Bernardo and Daniel Padilla)

Words such as Unfinished, GGSS, Low bat naba, Yangku which according to Wasta Fari (2010), the benefits it provides to the students because they continue to provide unique words that can be To further expand our knowledge, it has been a good result of studying this riser because it is proven that our language is rich and it is only proof.

Based on Lim's study (2009) proves that pidgin is alive because of the needs of a group such as the word hashtag, wakobet, ampunan kalurkey, Que and keri. Almario says our language is like peg, selfie, groufie but selfie is still topping the number 8 study so it's called the word of the year. According to Dr. Jovy Peregrino. "Jejemon and bekimese can stay or even disappear. And when and how, we cannot say it.

Finding shows the word most often used by *facebook, twitter and blog* users is as follows: selfie with which (8), hashtag (4), wakobet (4), peg (3), kalurkey (3), epek (3), anyare (3), push mo yan (3) groufie (3), emo (3), que (3), keri (3), ampatuan (3) PATROL on ABS-CBN (June 15, 2014) revived the constitution of 1987 so that this study proves that Filipinos are enriching the language based on the meaning and form of word formation and how to be creative in use of language like selfie which became the word of the year according to the 2014 probe.

Table 6. Chosen way in creating words used in Social Networking Site from the category of the elders, youth, gays, boys and girls.

Words used social networking site	Way of creating words in social networking site
#Throwback	Borrowed from the English word with the use of hashtag.
Aga muhlach	Using the name of a well-known personality.
Ampatuan	Using the name of a well-known personality.
Anong petsa na?	Onomatopoeia
Answeet	Removing the consonant word "G"
Anyare	Combined words of (Anong + Nangyare)
Aya	Borrowed from Ilokano word
CCTV	Usage of acronym
Chabelita	Addition of another word (ch -u + ab - by +elita)
Chismax	Combined words (Chika + to the max)
Cno siya ang lakas ng dating	A part of a song
Di ba pueding	Inventing words
Douglas MacArthur	Using the name of a well-known personality.
Emo	Shortened Words (emosyonal)
eOwh phFou	Jejemon sa salitang Hello Po. (Jejemon word for Hello)
Fulhaus	Pagbabaybay (full house)
GGSS	Paggamit ng akronim (Usage of acronym)
Groufie	Pinagsamang salitang (Group + selfie)/ combined words (Group + Selife)
Hairora boulevard	Pagkakahawig sa isang lugar
Istorya tupo tupo	Paghihiram ng buo sa Wikang Ilokano / (borrowed from Ilokano word)
Kalurkey	Pagbabago sa antas ng tunog (changing the tone of the word)
Kathniel	Pinagsamang pangalan ni (kathryn Bernardo + Daniel Padilla) / combination of the names (Kathryn Bernardo + Daniel Padilla)
Kemero	Pagpapaikli malayang nagpapalitan na "i" "e " (- Pa + k i - ala + mero) / Shortening or making the word short)
Keri	Gay word meaning can do.
Kuya Germs	Itinutulad sa pangalan ng personalidad. (Using the name of a well-known personality)
Kyotatalet	Pinapalitan ang unang titik/pantig ng mga salita gamit ang diptonggong("Ky-" + talet)/ (Changing the first letter or vowel of the word("Ky-" + talet)
Low bat naba	Pangihiram na may halong Filipino at Ingles/ (borrowing mix words from Filipino and English)

Lutong Makaw Madlang People	Read Between the lines statement Pinagsamang Filipino at Ingles/ (Combined words from Filipino and English)
Major Major Moom manes	Pag-uulit / (Repitition) Pagbabago sa antas ng tunog/ (Changing the sound of the words)
Ms. Undas Nakaka-gv	Read Between the lines statement Paggamit ng akronim/ (Usage of acronym)
Napoles Oblation	Salitang balbal na pera (Current Issues) Pagkakahawig sa isang lugar/bansa/ (similarities of one place or country)
Okray	Pagbibigay o pagdaragdag ng bagong kahulugan (Addition of new meaning)
Pag may time	Pag-iimbento ng salita/ (Invention of new sentence or word)
Push mo yan	Pag-iimbento ng salita/ (Invention of new sentence or word)
Pwamiz	Pagbabago sa antas ng tunog/ (Changing the sound of a word)
Que	Pag-iimbento ng salita sa isang grupo/ Invention of new word in one group)
Red alert	Pagkakahawig sa isang kulay/ (Having similarity on one color)
Selfie	Pagdaragdag sa salitang (self + patinig na i, e)/ Adding one word plus vowels (self+ i.e)
Shotimis ites	Metatesis (timi→itim) + pagbabago sa antas ng tunog (shotimis=timi; ites=ito)/ Changing the sound of a word)
Subit sina	Sabstitusyon (su=ka)/ (Substitution)
Tapsilog	Pagsasama ng salitang (tapa+sinangag+itlog)/(combining of the word (tapa+sinigang+itlog))
Wa learn	Pagpapaikli (wa=wala) at panghihiram ng buong anyo at kahulugan ng learn/ (Making the word short or borrowing the whole word and the meaning of it.)
Wakobet	Pagpapaikli (wa-wala) at panghihiram ng buong anyo at kahulugan ng bet/ (Making the word short or borrowing the whole word and the meaning of it.
Yakapsul	Pagsasama (Yakap+sul)/ (Combination of word)
Yangku	Pagbabaligtad ng salitang kuyang (Yang+ku)/(Reversing the word (Yang+Ku)

Based on this study, there have been new ways to develop and enrich the language in addition to the stated ways of learning by Evasco, et al. UP Diliman and Newmark such as Onomatopoeia, Appraisal of affixes, Word invention, Color identification, Gender coexistence and addition of suffixes, Constitution or variation of the first syllable and replaced with syllables ja, je, ji, jo, ju; cha, che, chi, cho, chu; or sha, she, shi, sho, shu and su, kyu, bu, borrowed of form but different meaning of attachment, foreign language borrowed, adding a new meaning based on something similar, language borrower from another language Philippines (Ilokano, Bikol, Cebuano, Gaddang, Itawes, Yogad), Adding meaning to words derived from the word it sounds, Borrowed with full form and meaning, Borrowed with full meaning with little difference in spelling Word integration, Jejemon, Similar to a song, Consciousness, Creation, Spelling, Abstract, Old-New Word and Changing.

It is only proof that the morphology and structure of the National Language are constantly changing and this is a proof that it was change that the persons' used the social media it was statistically and semantically shows on the research.

Based on the research findings, the researcher determine the most effective way of building words on social networking sites. Seven (7) most commonly used methods of generating words abbreviation (49) rank number 1, followed by borrowed word from different language with (31) rank 2, word multiplication with (30 rank 3), word invention with (28) rank 4, likeness to personality (21) rank 5, add word from the original text with (20) rank 6, Jejemons spelling(35) rank 7. The Social Networking Site enriched the Filipino language because different languages of the Philippines in Ilocano, Bicol, and Cebuano language actively express their language identities based on this research it is a proof that their language is continuously cultivated in by expressing a social networking site. English, Japanese, and Spanish are used in social networking sites in a creative way so that it is proof that our language is active, dynamic or changing and as time goes by it flows but depend on what language the user will use and based on Republic Act rules and regulations in Republic Law no. 7104 creates a Filipino language commission. The commission will take into account the native languages and other languages spoken by the Filipinos so that if the structure (morphology) and the form of words are continuously increased based on who uses the language.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

There are so many new words sprouting through social networking sites, strange and new words become widespread in the mass. Words used on the social networking site prove that the lexicon of Filipino is developing and there is a big impact on the millennial user and adult. The meaning of the word has resulted in a broad understanding and is reviewed to be consulted in these languages which are clearly defined. The ways in which the Filipino language is structured is increasing. The language of the social networking site has been given a unique taste of the user by its creative use.

Based on the result of the research, the researcher is recommending for a deeper study on the following aspects:

1. Inculcate to have a good knowledge of the Filipino language structure (morphology);
2. Revive, enrich and promote these localized Idiolect and Sociolect for the next generation;
3. Find out more social networking sites that contribute to language enrichment;
4. Analyze the whole research to be able to deepen how Bekimon affects the people in social media;
5. Give attention and importance to the comprehensive result of the research to create a mini-reference dictionary in order to identify

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